

The Peculiarities of Physical Education Programme (5–9 Grades) in Ukraine

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Abstract

This work's aim to present the peculiarities modern of Physical Education Programme (5–9 Grades) in Ukraine. The carried out analysis of the launched PE program of Ukrainian (2009) allows us to confirm that the given program is characterised by its direction towards variant principle realisation that foresees teaching materials planning in accordance with age and sex peculiarities of students, their interests, financial and technical provision of the teaching process and personnel supplying. Programme is aimed at the realisation of educational, upbringing, health-improving, developing target in PE teaching process as well as keeping to didactic principles of teaching: understanding and activity, visual aids, comprehension and individualization, system and sequence, durability and scientism.

Key words: Physical Education, Program, Ukraine, 5-9 Grades, module.

Introduction

The beginning of the 21st century in Europe is characterized by a considerable change in educational policy and a number of significant reforms in the field of education. The present day is characterised by a clear-cut tendency of the majority educational systems' integration into the European space of general education. The reforming of Ukrainian educational system hasn't become on exceptional, which has touched upon Physical Education as a subject, being natural part of teaching and upbringing process at school and benefiting the all-raund development of school children including their health strengthening and physical and spiritual qualities improvement.

The practical solution of these tasks is possible only in case of educational process effective planning which to great extent depends on quality of program. At the same time many scientists think that the existing PE programs in Ukraine didn't meet the school children's demands and was not suitable for the formation of durable interest to PE classes [1, 4, 7, 8, 9].

Thus, during the thesis research made by Г.В. Безверхня (in 2004) it was found out that, unfortunate, about 50% of Ukrainian children lack their durable interest to PE classes [2].

The main reasons are as follows:

- as physical exercises choice the schoolchildren interests are not taken into consideration being strictly regulated by the state program;
- modern means of physical and health-improvement work are not being used;
- age-group individual development peculiarities are being ignored;
- physical loading concerning children's health state, and level of their physical preparedness are not being differentiated;
- the level of schools' financial and technical provision is being low;
- the pupils' effective assessment system has not been worked out yet.

That's why, active search for new methods that could activate pupils' interest to PE classes has been recently done in Ukraine. As a result, a new program (5–9 Grades), based on theoretic-

cal and practical acquirement of Ukrainian specialists and leading European countries experience in the field of PE, has been worked out.

The aim of the research paper has been to analyze the new PE teaching programme (5–9 Grades) functioning in Ukraine.

In the process of the given investigation there have been used the following research methods: methods of theoretical analyses and generalization of scientific methodical literature data and official documents.

Physical Education Programme

Since 2009/2010 academic year in Ukrainian schools, there has been launched the new PE program [6].

It's worth mentioning that like in the majority of European countries in Ukrainian schools after the reforms children stay at school for 12 years. Teaching period (one academic hour equals 45 minutes) in grades 5–9 corresponds to the following age limits:

- grade 5 – 10 years old,
- grade 6 – 11 years old,
- grade 7 – 12 years old,
- grade 8 – 13 years old,
- grade 9 – 14 years old.

Typical teaching plans for secondary educational establishments of Ukraine allocate for PE subject [5]:

- in grades 5–7: 2,5 hours per week (in Ukraine language secondary educational establishments) and 2 hours per week (in Russian language or other national minority language schools or in Ukraine language plus two foreign languages schools),
- in grades 8–9: 3 hours per week,
- in grades 5–7, the following variants of hours division are the most popular in Ukraine schools:

Variant 1: Week 1–2 hours, week 2–3 (Term 1 and Term 2).

Variant 2: Term 1–2 hours per week; Term 2–3 hours per week (or vice versa)

Variant 3: While learning track-and-field athletics materials and sports games at the stadiums and play grounds (the beginning of the first term and the end of the end of the second term) – 3 hours.

While learning gymnastics materials, sports games in school gyms (the end of the first and she beginning of the 2nd term) – 2 hours.

The main documents of the teaching process in Ukrainian schools are the following ones:

- teaching programme;
- teaching plan of a secondary school;
- scheme of materials division and coverage;
- working plan of a teaching programme realization, which is made for half a year or the whole year;
- detailed plan of a lesson or a system of lessons.

A lesson is the main form of physical education teaching process organization in a secondary school of Ukraine.

At physical education lessons in Ukraine schools there takes place interrelationship between such subjects as Anatomy and Physiology of a Human Being, Hygiene, Physics, physical education theory and teaching methods, History of Physical Education and Sports, music, choreography and etc.

The contents of physical education as the subject are aimed at the formation of key competences in schoolchildren; such as: sociable (ability to cooperate solution of life problems, mutual understanding social activity, formation of physical culture in individual; basics of healthy lifestyle); motivation (formation of societal and individual understanding of excellent health prestige and physical preparedness, ability to study/learn, display of creativity in various movements in conditions of different complexity levels, adaptability) and functional (ability to make use of the knowledge on natural movement activity, knowledge of Physical Culture and Sports history, enrichment of movement experience with the aim of physical qualities and movement skills in accordance with age peculiarities, mastering of terminology and methodology competences), which illustrate the hierarchy of demands as for sporting activities that are gradually developing and improving.

However, the complex solution of physical education students' tasks foresees not only class forms of lessons in Grades 5–9, but out-of-school ones as well.

To the main out-of-class Physical Education forms belong:

- health improving classes in the day routine (sports minutes, sports breaks during teaching process, health hour, etc.);
- after classes lessons (competitions in accordance with school programme, sport-artistic holidays, health days);
- out-of-school activities (classes in sports groups and sections, sports schools, out-of-school sports organization interest clubs, under parents' guidance, etc.).

Ukraine school teachers of physical education are obliged not only to run physical education compulsory lessons, but provide teaching methods, organization and carrying out-of-class health improving and sporting work that foresees:

- composing a set of physical education minutes and assistance in their organization realization during lessons;
- giving methodical assistance both teachers and schoolchildren as for carrying out other forms of health-improving and sporting work within a school day;
- organization of a sports club activities and joint preparation for sporting events and competitions confirmed by a school council, including the kinds of sport foresees by school programme;
- organization of a sports section work based on either traditional for the given school kind of sport or chosen by students;
- training organization and provision school teams participation in different competitions.

Before a new academic year starts schoolchildren must go through a thorough check up. In accordance with its results of medical check-up temporary Ukrainian school children are subdivided into PE medical groups: the main, preparatory and special ones.

To the main group belong the children without health deviations or with some insignificant deviations but with enough deviations or with some insignificant deviations but with enough physical training.

The prep medical group is composed of the pupils who have some insignificant deviations in their health and physical development, but lack physical training.

To the special medical group belong the children with considerable deviations in their

health with disagree with serious loading. Such pupils are taught in accordance with a special program.

Those pupils who become of their health state haven't been listed in the main medical group, are to attend PE classes in case they do correction exercises or those ones for their general development that agree with them.

The new PE program in Ukraine is based on module system. It is composed of two compulsory modules: theoretical-methodical knowledge and general physical training plus some variant modules: track-and-field athletics, gymnastics, swimming, football, basketball, handball, tourism, aerobics, badminton, etc.

Theoretical and methodical knowledge embraces four units students must master: knowledge connected with a healthy mode of life, knowledge of organizing and methodical character, the basics of self-control, as well as Olympic education problems. For example, the fifth-grade students must know: the general characteristics of a healthy mode of life; hygiene and sanitation rules observation during physical education classes, types of stature discords and their avoidance, safety rules in class and out-of-class, to have an idea about physical development physical training and self-control basics during the performance of physical exercises, as well as to be informed about physical education in Ancient Greece.

Practically, each sports can be represented as a variant module. PE specialists can make variant modules of their own for this program. These variant modules can undergo the Ministry for Education and Science of Ukraine expertise. Hence, the number of variant modules will grow meanwhile.

The contents of the subject "Physical Education" are made of variant modules by an educational establishment independently. However, means of theoretical and physical training, foreseen by the program for each grade and variant module, are compulsory.

In Grade 5–6: students must cover 4–6 variant modules, in Grades 7–8: 3–5 modules, and in Grade 9: 3–4 ones. More or less equal quantity of time is allotted to the coverage of all modules. Thus, in Grade 5 with 6 chosen modules and 105 hours per year, 18 hours are

given per module. But, the new PE program in Ukraine permits to increase or decrease the number of hours allotted to each module.

Variant module program are made for a 5-year period. They contain an Explanatory Note, teaching materials contents, state demands to secondary school students training, oriented standards and a list of sports equipment necessary for the module coverage.

At the beginning of an academic year the protocol of school methodical of Ukraine confirms the schedule-plan of PE variant modules for each grade. The plan contains variant modules to be covered by students, the year of their study and the number of allotted hours. The study process starts in Grade 5.

The criteria of variant modules selection include: the availability of financial and technical base, regional sports traditions, personnel staff and students wishes. The students' wishes are defined by a compulsory questionnaire at the end of an academic year. The questionnaire results should be added to the school methodical group protocol.

In the process variant modules may be modified.

For example, students study:

- in Grade 5 – football (first year), volleyball (first year), track-and-field (first year), swimming (first year) and skiing training (first year);
- in Grade 6 – football (second year), volleyball (second year), swimming (second year) and skiing training (first year), track-and-field (second year) and badminton (first year);
- in Grade 7 – football (third year), track-and-field (third year), swimming (third year) and badminton (second year);
- in Grade 8 – football (forth year), table tennis (first year), gymnastics (first year), and basketball (first year);
- in Grade 9 – football (fifth year), gymnastics (second year), and basketball (second year).

If it is necessary, in Grades 6–9 the program foresees the coverage of a 2-year material within one variant module.

If two variant modules are studied within one academic year or in case the module studies begin later (not in Grade 5) a teacher should correct the modules contents and their assessment.

Home tasks play an important in Ukraine schools' physical education classes organization. It should be directed at the improvement of movement regime in free time, as well as, achievement of recreational and health-improving effect. In case of physical development qualities lag, a teacher (in Grades 8 and 9 together with a student) should make an individual programme of physical health-improving classes which define tasks, physical exercises, their performance sequence, repetition number, breaks for rest, means of self-control, performance assessment. Independent classes, based on the individual programme will give a student extra bonuses while assessing the result/achievements.

It is not recommended to double physical education lessons or run then day after day while composing a time-table. The majority of physical education lessons should be taught in the open air.

The assessment of PE students achievements in Ukraine should be performed in the following way:

- acquiring physical exercises technique;
- the performance of standards (considering the dynamics of personal results;
- performance of tasks during a lesson;
- gaining theoretical and methodical knowledge.

What is more, the mark given for the standard performance isn't a dominant one during thematic, term or year assessment.

For the assessment of physical qualities there have been used program standards created for each academic year. Test standards are only oriented ones. The order of their realization is defined by a teacher in accordance with his/her calendar thematic planning.

The achievement level (beginner, average, sufficient, high) is defined by standard indicator, and then by technical index of movement performance and theoretical knowledge resulting in assessment points [3].

When assessing PE standards, school teachers of Ukraine should keep to the following demands:

Program standards are demonstrated by the main medical group students who don't complain of their poor health, at the moment of their demonstration.

Each test exercise should be preceded by physical training (at least during 2 classes).

Before the test, teacher should warm the students up, then do refreshing exercises.

Students are allowed to retake their standards test at the lesson defined by the teacher.

A teacher must provide absolute safety rules keeping and their realization during standards demonstration.

When assessing PE achievements there should be taken into consideration the following things: individual achievements of a student within academic year; the degree of their activity; out-of-class PE lessons encouragement; participation in all kinds of contests. On the basis of the above mentioned indexes teacher can apply different "bonus" points system. For example, if a student did the test exercise at a certain level, but at the same time his/her individual result of that exercise performance has improved in comparison with the earlier result, a teacher is allowed to give him/her 1 or 2 points more than it is foreseen by program standards.

Between the first of September and the first of October, annually, in order to adapt students to PE lessons loading, the test standards are not assessed; but PE classes are of recreational

and health-improving character, with moderate loading.

Conclusions

Thus, the carried out analysis of the launched PE program of Ukrainian (2009) allows us to confirm that the given program: is aimed at the realization of educational, upbringing, health-improving, developing target in PE teaching process as well as keeping to didactic principles of teaching: understanding and activity, visual aids, comprehension and individualization, system and sequence, durability and scientism; allows teachers to make a differentiation approach to the teaching process organization considering students health state, stages of their physical development, movement preparation and sex, as well as, their motifs and interests to perform physical exercises; forms in students skills and abilities to do physical exercises on their own; is characterized by its direction towards variant principle realisation that foresees teaching materials planning in accordance with age and sex peculiarities of students, their interests, financial and technical provision of the teaching process (a gymnasium, school sports grounds, a stadium, a swimming pool, etc.) and personnel supplying.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Арефев В., Єдинак Г. (2007). *Фізична культура в школі(молодому спеціалісту)*. №-3 вид. Кам'янець Подільський, Рута.
2. Безверхня Г.В. (2004). *Мотивація до занять фізичною культурою і спортом школярів 5–11-х класів*. Дис. канд. наук з фіз. виховання і спорту: 24.00.02. Умань, Уманський держ. педагогічний університет.
3. Критерії оцінювання навчальних досягнень учнів із фізичної культури затверджені наказом МОН України, від 05.05.08 № 371.
4. Круцевич Т.Ю. (2008). *Теорія і методика фізичного виховання*. Київ, Олімпійська література.
5. *Типові навчальні плани для загальноосвітніх навчальних закладів*. (2009). Наказ Міністерства освіти і науки України, від 05.02.2009 р., № 66.
6. *Фізична культура в школі – методичний посібник*. (2009). Київ, Літера ЛТД.
7. Худолій О.М. (2008). *Загальні основи теорії та методики фізичного виховання*. Харків, ОВС.
8. *Фізична культура – програма для загальноосвітніх навчальних закладів 5–12 класи*. (2005). Перун, ВТФ.
9. Шиян Б.М. (2008). *Теорія і методика фізичного виховання школярів*. Тернопіль, Навчальна книга Бог-дан.

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